

GREEN BUSINESS MODELS AND ENTREPRENEURIAL INITIATIVES OF BAKERY BUSINESSES IN PORT HARCOURT, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurial initiatives increasingly influence the adoption of green business models, promoting environmental sustainability and innovation among small and medium-sized enterprises. This study examined how entrepreneurial initiatives foster green business models in bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, focusing on creativity, risk-taking, and research and development (R&D) activities. The study specifically aimed to determine the relationship between green business models and (i) creativity, (ii) risk-taking, and (iii) R&D activities among bakery businesses. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of 180 registered bakery businesses within Port Harcourt, from which a sample of 123 respondents was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula. Data were collected using the structured Entrepreneurial Initiatives and Green Business Models Questionnaire (EIGBMQ), validated by experts and tested for reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.82). Questionnaires were administered directly, yielding 117 usable responses (95.1% response rate). Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage) and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation were employed to analyze data and test hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. The results revealed significant positive relationships between green business models and creativity ($r = 0.68$), risk-taking ($r = 0.62$), and R&D activities ($r = 0.71$). These findings suggest that adopting green business practices enhances innovative capabilities, encourages calculated risk-taking, and stimulates continuous research and development in bakery businesses. The study concluded that green business models serve as strategic tools for improving entrepreneurial performance and sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

Rising concerns such as climate change, resource depletion, environmental protection, and social inequality are reshaping global expectations of how business organizations should operate. Within this evolving landscape, green business models have emerged as powerful frameworks for aligning profitability with environmental stewardship and social

responsibility (Solesvik, Torgersen, Andersson, & Valter, 2022). At the same time, entrepreneurial initiatives are playing a pivotal role in driving the transition toward sustainability by introducing innovative solutions and challenging conventional practices that not only enhance the ease of doing business but also are human and environmentally friendly (López-Solís, Luzuriaga-Jaramillo, Bedoya-Jara, Naranjo-Santamaría, Bonilla-Jurado & Acosta-Vargas, 2025; Lindgren, Knoth, Sureshkumar, Friedrich, & Adomaityte, 2021). This indeed is a paradigm shift from the traditional ways business activities have been conducted in the past.

Over the past few decades, the operational activities of business organizations have left a significant environmental footprint, particularly in the extractive and manufacturing sectors, resulting in serious damages such as carbon emissions and water pollution. This has led to the United Nations Conference on the Environment in Stockholm in 1972 (Lamprey, Owusu-Manu, Acheampong, Adesi & Ghansah, 2021). This conference and subsequent conferences did not yield much benefit until the increase in agitation by concerned individuals, businesses, and very informed consumers in developed countries began to agitate for the protection of the environment. Regional blocs like the European Union (EU), Association of South-East Asian Nations (ASEAN), Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), etc., and governments of developed and developing countries like the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, India, the United Arab Emirates, etc., also began to roll out policies to protect the environment.

Some of these activities to protect the environment include, but are not limited to, the Energy and Research Institute (TERI) India, which specializes in the field of energy, environment, and sustainable development, the Great Green Walls specializes in combating desertification and planting of trees, Modou Fall's Advocacy, which educates people about the dangers of plastics to the environment, and the Ocean Cleanup Initiatives responsible for the protection of the aquatic lives from the dangers of plastics. Other policies to protect the environment for corporate organizations include sustainable practices, eco-friendly products, and corporate social responsibility. For individuals, include reducing, reusing, recycling wastes, supporting the conservation of habitats, and being sustainable (Rizos, Behrens, Van der Gaast, Hofman, Ioannou, Kafyeke, Flamos, Roberto Rinaldi, Papadelis, Hirschnitz-Garbers & Topi, 2016; Voland, Saad, & Eicker, 2022).

This study seek to explore the intersection between green business models and entrepreneurial initiatives, the concepts, principles, and practical applications, highlighting their importance for businesses in contemporary day, discusses challenges in the 21st century to their adoption, strategies for their effective implementation, and future directions.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine how entrepreneurial initiatives foster green business models among bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the relationship between green business models and the creativity of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the relationship between green business models and the risk-taking of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.
- iii. Assess the relationship between green business models and the research and development activities of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between green business models and the creativity of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between green business models and the risk-taking of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the relationship between green business models and research and development of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between green business models and the creativity of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between green business models and the risk-taking of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between green business models and the research and development activities of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

The Clayton Christensen Institute Business Model Theory

This theory identifies four interlocking elements that, when put together, create and deliver value. These include value proposition, resources, process, and profit formula or priorities. This theory argues that innovation and creativity create markets to be satisfied, thereby making room for the first element, which is the value proposition, and an organization sets a value that it promises to offer to its customers, such as low-cost products, simpler products, etc. This will then require the second element, which is resources to achieve these promises, which include assets, technology, skills, etc. They further argued that as this value proposition is made, over time, this organization develops a method that is processed, with which they deliver their promise. This process element is the third element, and they argued that it is the habitual ways that the organization has developed over time, and that some processes are documented while some are not. The process element may include planning, budgeting, training, etc.

They further proposed that for the organization to cover all the costs they have incurred in going through these other three elements, a fourth element is born, which is the profit formula. This, they posited, will enhance sustainability. This defines how the organization will maintain viability and sustainability over time in the delivery of the promises made to its customers with its resources. They warned that organizations should be aware of potential disruptors in their industry and consider how they might respond or adapt, and also that organizations should be aware of potential disruptors in the industry they operate in and consider how they might respond or adapt to these changes. Also, they warned that organizations should understand the needs of unmet customers, as it can lead to innovative solutions that disrupt existing markets. This model emphasizes the importance of recognizing and adapting to disruptive innovations and that the organizations that successfully navigate

through these changes can secure a competitive advantage and thrive in rapidly evolving markets.

The Extinction Avoidance Theory

The Avoidance Theory is oftentimes explored in the context of avoidance conditioning; its root dates back to early research in the 1930s that focused on understanding fear and anxiety. The originator of this theory was not mentioned; however, it builds on the concepts of behavioral psychology that were introduced by researchers in the past years. This theory argues that resources (both natural and man-made) can be depleted over time due to neglect or improper use. It postulates that good behaviors or strategies can be employed to prevent the extinction of these resources, especially in ecological or economic contexts. It further emphasizes that there should be a balance between present needs and future resource availability. This theory has applications across social science and other disciplines, especially on how resources like financial, technological, and human capital are acquired and preserved for both present and future uses.

This theory is significant in many ways as it acknowledges the finite feature of both natural and man-made resources, advocates for behaviors and strategies that will ensure the sustainability of these resources, and also avoids their potential extinction in various media. Many scientific studies have examined and argued in support of the implications and applications of extinction avoidance strategies in preserving both biological species and economic systems, thereby addressing broader sustainability issues. Other theories related to the extinction avoidance theory include the rogue agent theory, the collective stewardship theory, the divine intervention and providence theory, and the resource-resilient world theory.

Green business models

Shinde, Khandare, Kale, & Nalbalwar (2025) defined a green business model as a strategic framework in which business organizations design their business activities, products, and services to minimize negative environmental impacts and maximize social and economic values. Unlike traditional models that focus primarily on financial returns, green business models adopt a triple bottom line approach—measuring success in terms of profit, people, and planet. A business model that contributes to a green economy by promoting sustainable practices, reducing environmental impact, and generating economic benefits (Al-Taai, 2021; Houssam, Ibrahim, Sucharita, El-Aasar, Esily, & Sethi, 2023). It also focuses on environmental sustainability, reducing waste, and promoting eco-friendly products or services (Pasaribu, 2024; Udodiugwu, Obiakor, Eneremadu, Onwuegbuchulem, & Anyaegbunam, 2025).

Green business models prioritizes long-term sustainability (Pahlevi & Suhartanto, 2020; Khandare, 2024; Munir, T., & Watts, 2025; Odeyemi, Usman, Mhlongo, Elufioye, & Ike, 2024; Kulkarni, Valeri, & William, 2025), minimizes environmental degradation, and promotes social responsibility (Goyal, Esposito, & Kapoor, 2018; Katsikeas, Leonidou, & Zeriti, 2016; Sumrin, Gupta, Asaad, Wang, Bhattacharya, & Foroudi, 2021; Vangeri, Bathrinath, Anand, Shanmugathai, Meenatchi, & Boopathi, 2024), incorporates sustainable practices (Comin, Aguiar, Sehnem, Yusliza, Cazella, & Julkovski, 2020; Khalid, 2023; Upadhyay, Kumar, Kumar, & Alzaben, 2021; Sarana, 2024; Koval, AleksieienkoLemovska, & Mikhno, (2023; Jadhav, Pandey, Pawar, & Kadam, 2025), reduces environmental impact, and promotes eco-friendly products or services (Huang, 2024; Abdellatif, Hicham, & Karim, 2024; Bandh, Malla, Wani, & Hoang, 2024).

The adoption of green business models varies depending on the industry, the strategy an organization seeks to adopt in achieving it, and the market it chooses to focus on (Purwandani & Michaud, 2021; Chatzoglou & Chatzoudes, 2016; Wasiq, M., Kamal, & Ali, 2023). Businesses may choose to provide direct services to consumers instead of selling the product outright, thereby reducing material waste - Product-Service System, or using renewable, recyclable, or biodegradable resources in their production – Circular Supply Models, transforming wastes into valuable assets by creating other ways that waste products can be used - Waste-to-Value Models, businesses investing in eco-friendly technologies such as electric vehicles – Green Technology Innovation, and investing in a blend of business that shares profits with their host communities - Social Enterprises with Environmental Goals (Yin, Yu, & Zhang, 2024; Prabhu, 2021; Esparza, Madrid-Guijarro, & Maldonado-Guzman, 2025).

Resource optimization and costs reduction at the long run (Liu, 2025; Whalen, 2019), proactiveness in the compliance of the evolving environmental and human protection laws (Gu, & Xie, 2022; Chang, 2015), having access to the many financial resources available to those complying (Munir, & Fausiah, 2025; Ullah, Ahmad, Rizwan, & Khattak, 2024), engenders innovativeness and creativity, which translates to business sustainability (Qalati, 2025) are some benefits enjoyed by those that adopt the green business model. Many authors and entrepreneurs have argued that, in spite of the numerous benefits of this environmentally friendly method of doing business, also, there are many challenges to their adoption. This includes, but is not limited to, high investment costs, employees, suppliers, and consumers' resistance to change, the different tastes of consumers' demand for green products, and the complex nature of the supply chains (Asem, Mensah-Bonsu, Egyir, Adom, & Aawulena, 2025; Zong, & Guan, 2025).

Troise, Santoro, & Bresciani, (2024) identified in their article titled “Small and medium enterprises and sustainable business models: Exploring enabling factors for adoption” some enablers of green business models as, leadership commitment to change, stakeholders' collaboration, incremental change, transparency in reporting the organization's sustainability so as to build trust and accountability, and the adoption of the use of digital technologies (block chain technologies, Internet of Things (IoT), etc. Looking ahead, green business models will be pivotal to global economic resilience. With the increase in climate regulations, consumer awareness, and the rise of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) metrics, businesses that fail to adopt the green business practices stands to lose relevance. Also, the future trends of the Green Business Models include wider adoption of closed-loop economic practices, growth in renewable energy markets, and stronger integration of green innovation in emerging economies.

Entrepreneurial initiatives

Entrepreneurial initiatives refer to the proactive approach that is taken by individuals or groups of people in an organization in identifying opportunities, new creative ventures, and driving business growth (Pavlenko, Kucher, Holovina, Kniaz, Shayda, Franiv, & Dzvonyk, 2021; De Clercq, Castañer, & Belausteguigoitia, 2011; Ratten, 2023; van Lunenburg, 2025; Sekliuckiene, & Kisielius, 2015; Nsereko, Balunywa, Ntamu, Munene, & Babirye, 2021; Ignacio, Pilar, & Enrique, 2024; Ben Chikha, Salloum, El Hilali, & Jarboui, 2025). This concept has become significant in the contemporary, rapidly dynamic business environment, where innovativeness, creativity, and adaptability are crucial for an organization's success. This article will navigate the significance, key components, the challenges faced by entrepreneurs, and the impact of entrepreneurial initiatives on both society and the economy.

Entrepreneurial initiatives drive innovation and are usually the birthplace of innovative ideas and technological breakthroughs. It is not limited to the use of technology and spans various sectors (Khan, Mavondo, & Zahoor, 2025). It encourages growth and job creation as new businesses create jobs, increase competition, and foster productivity. According to the United States Small Business Administration, SMEs create two-thirds of the new jobs in the economy (Ferreira & Ferreira, 2025; Terziev, Lyubcheva, Andreeva, Georgiev, Simeonov, & Dimitrov, 2025). Also, it addresses social issues and community development. Some businesses address issues that solve problems in society, thereby encouraging growth and development. For instance, social entrepreneurs like TOMS shoes that adopt a “one-for-one” model by donating shoes to the less privileged to improve the quality of life of the less privileged in society.

This concept of entrepreneurial initiatives cannot just evolve overnight; it requires certain key elements to be operational. An entrepreneurial initiative must begin with a clear vision and creativity to turn ideas into reality (Pita, Costa, & Moreira, 2021; Nikiforova, & Polyakov, 2022). Another vital component is risk-taking and resilience. Entrepreneurship involves risk-taking in the achievement of business goals, and it requires finance, commitment, and the potential for failure. Resilience, therefore, is important as businesses face many setbacks, and the ability to learn from failures and adopt new strategies becomes a hallmark of success (Elia, Margherita, & Passiante, 2020). Lastly, Networking and collaboration as entrepreneurs benefit from mentors, industry experts, and other businesses for their success. Building a strong network can lead to a new set of opportunities, partnerships, and access to resources that may ordinarily be available standing alone (Ataei, Karimi, Ghadermarzi, & Norouzi, 2020).

There are a plethora of obstacles faced by entrepreneurs such as limited access to financial resources, stiff market competition, and too many regulatory and compliance issues that do not favor the business (Shimizu, & Madden, 2025). Entrepreneurial initiative affects our world in many ways, such as empowerment and economic independence, enhancing sustainability and environmental responsibility, and encouraging cultural and social diversity. As we continue to navigate an increasingly dynamic and complex world, and the need to make our environment more sustainable and hazard-free, it is pertinent that we support and encourage entrepreneurial initiative in building resilient economies and thriving communities, and contribute to a brighter future for all.

Measures of Entrepreneurial Initiatives

Creativity

Creativity is the tendency to generate or recognize ideas, other alternatives, or possibilities that may help solve problems, communicate with others, and entertain ourselves and others (Brauer, Ormiston, & Beausaert, 2025). It is also the ability to bring novel and valuable ideas or works from the imagination of an individual or a group of people, which can be transformed into both tangible and intangible products. Creativity, therefore, is a multifaceted concept that transcends mere expression and can be defined as the ability to generate new ideas, approaches, or introduce valuable new solutions (Arifudin, Bumbungan, & Kartika, 2025). Barth, & Stadtmann (2025) argued that it involves the interplay of imagination, knowledge, and skills to create something distinct. This concept holds countless significance for businesses as it enables them to remain viable in the face of a dynamic and challenging business landscape.

Creative thinking leads to innovative ideas, organizational adaptability, self-expression, and overall fulfillment, while encouraging collaboration (Tolkamp, Verwaeren, Vriend, Riekhoff,

& Nijstad, 2025). While some scholars hold the view that creativity is an innate talent, others believe it can be nurtured through learning, collaboration, and training. They believe that entrepreneurs can encourage creativity by embracing curiosity, creating a supportive environment, practicing mindfulness, and allowing risk-taking activities (Ding, & Li, 2025; Franceschelli & Musolesi, 2025; Zhang, L., Lin, & Oon, 2025). By understanding the concept and importance of creativity, individuals can unlock their hidden creative potential, contributing to innovation and development in their professional lives. It is a vital skill that is essential for everyone and offers numerous benefits, including improved communication, enhanced problem-solving abilities, and increased adaptability in various situations.

Risk-taking

Entrepreneurs do not merely take risks; they take calculated risks. In other words, not every risk that entrepreneurs take is arbitrary. Risk-taking involves making decisions under fast-changing conditions, where the potential for loss or failure exists alongside the possibility of rewards (Field, Nagy, Knaggs & Collett, 2024; Zhao, 2024). Risk-taking can be defined as any behavior, whether consciously or unconsciously controlled, that involves a perceived uncertainty regarding its outcomes and the potential benefits or costs associated with it. This can impact the physical, economic, or psycho-social well-being of oneself or others (Trimpop, 1994). The degree of risk businesses take differs, and the degree of risk a business takes depends on how volatile a company's Return on Assets (ROA) was over the observation period (Liu, Zhao, & Kong, 2023).

However, some strategies can be adopted for effective risk-taking for the benefit of the business. They include proper assessment of risks, success rates, and impact of failure on the business starting with a smaller manageable size of risks and gradually increasing it, viewing failure not as a setback, but as a chance to learn from past experiences and an opportunity for growth, and having a supportive network can make taking risks feel less intimidating (Swanton, Blaszczyński, Forlini, Starcevic, & Gainsbury, 2021; Man, Chan, Alabdulkarim, & Zhang, 2021). Risk-taking can be in the following areas, such as new business ventures to invest capital and time into new ideas, career moves for professionals who want to switch jobs, acquire new skills, etc., or in the area of personal relationships, where managers create new relationships, make new connections, or open up to others.

Risk-taking is essential for growth and innovation. Managers who fear risks may hold themselves back; however, those who embrace this concept ultimately thrive.

Research and Development (R&D)

R&D involves a systematic approach to investigation and experimentation, focusing on uncovering new knowledge or creativity by applying existing knowledge (Borden, & Torstrick, 2025). Risk-taking in business is significant as it fosters creativity and innovation, builds resilience (Tomova, Andrews, & Blakemore, 2021; Tomova, Andrews, & Blakemore, 2021), sharpens the ability of individuals in managing and weighing potential outcomes (Bauer, Bernanke, & Milstein, 2023; Wang, Liu, & Luo, 2021), analyzing them and considers the best for adoption, and also creates many opportunities as new ways of doing business or a new kind of business might emerge (Armstrong-Carter, & Telzer, 2025; Zhang & Wang, 2025; Geng, Su, & Wang, 2025; Willoughby, Heffer, Good, & Magnacca, 2021; Huang, Ma, & Wang, 2022).

R&D can be defined as a systematic exploration and experimentation focused on uncovering new knowledge or applying existing knowledge in creative ways (Borden & Torstrick, 2025; Gressler, Hipfinger, Part, Pavlicek, Zafiu, & Giese, 2025). The research phase emphasizes

essential scientific questions and theories, aiming to enhance the understanding of phenomena, develop new concepts, and produce insights that can result in practical applications. In contrast, the development phase focuses on the translation of research outcomes into useful applications, which include new products, new or improved methods, or technologies. R&D is significant to every organization, as some of the benefits include giving the business an innovative and competitive advantage, causing economic growth of the organization (Wingate, 2025).

It also contributes to problem-solving, as many of the world's challenges have been addressed through research and development (R&D). This process leads to scientific advancements, enabling the invention of new methods, products, or processes. Additionally, some companies may not have the time to wait for R&D to produce results, which can discourage stakeholders. The risk of failure is also a concern, as many R&D efforts do not result in successful outcomes, thereby deterring investments (Bataineh, Sánchez-Sellero, & Ayad, 2024). As the business landscape continues to evolve, the significance of R&D will continue to grow, and organizations that invest in R&D will enjoy a competitive advantage and contribute to the broader economic and scientific progress in

Green Business Models and Entrepreneurship Initiatives

Aleksy Kwilinski, Oleksii Lyulyov, and Tetyana Pimonenko (2024) examined the impact of entrepreneurial transformation on achieving green economic development in EU countries during the period from 2007 to 2022. Researchers utilized the Malmquist-Lueberger productivity index to measure green economic development and employed fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS), dynamic ordinary least squares (DOLS), and both systems and first difference generalized method of moments (GMM) to assess the effect of entrepreneurial transformation on green economic development. The findings indicated a strong positive relationship between green economic development and entrepreneurship development.

Prokopenko, Chechel, Koldovskiy, & Kldiashvili (2024) analyzed green entrepreneurship models and highlighted successful initiatives in various regions, including those related to solar energy, green agriculture, and green product development startups, to understand the impact related to social, economic, and environmental factors. The findings of the study indicated that creativity is an important business strategy, partnerships in the strategic plan, the application of technology, and capturing communities in driving green entrepreneurship. Tekala, Baradarani, Alzubi, & Berberoğlu (2024) explored the effect of green entrepreneurship (GEN) on business sustainability (BS), focusing on the mediating role of green structural capital (GSC) and the moderating influence of environmental dynamism (ED) in various sectors in Istanbul and Izmir, Turkey. The results indicated that GEN significantly enhances BS and GSC, with GSC serving as an important mediator. However, ED negatively moderates the GEN-BS relationship, implying that GEN's positive impact on BS is stronger in less uncertain environments.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which was considered appropriate because it enabled the systematic collection of data from respondents on entrepreneurial initiatives and green business models without manipulating any variables. The population of the study consisted of all registered bakery businesses operating within Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, Nigeria. The population frame was compiled from records obtained from the Rivers State Ministry of Commerce and Industry, local bakery associations, and municipal business registration offices, which jointly provided a reliable listing of active

bakeries operating within the study area. Through this process, a total of 180 registered bakery businesses were identified. The choice of bakery businesses was informed by their significant contribution to food production, environmental waste generation, and growing interest in sustainable business practices within urban Nigeria (Adeleke & Aminu, 2021; Eneh, 2019).

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select respondents for the study. In the first stage, Port Harcourt metropolis was purposively selected due to its high concentration of bakery enterprises. In the second stage, simple random sampling was used to select bakery businesses from the compiled population list. The sample size was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination formula, which recommends a sample of 123 respondents for a population of 180 at a 95% confidence level. Consequently, 123 owner-managers or senior staff of bakery businesses were selected as respondents. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled "Entrepreneurial Initiatives and Green Business Models Questionnaire (EIGBMQ)". The instrument was validated through face and content validity by experts in entrepreneurship and environmental management. Reliability was established using the Cronbach's Alpha method, which yielded a coefficient of 0.82, indicating a high level of internal consistency.

The questionnaires were administered using a direct, hand-delivery method, which ensured a higher response rate and allowed for clarification where necessary. Out of the 123 questionnaires distributed, 117 were correctly completed and returned, representing a 95.1% response rate, and these were used for data analysis. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics, specifically the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, to test the stated hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. This analytical approach enabled the study to establish the nature and strength of relationships between entrepreneurial initiatives and green business models among bakery businesses in Port Harcourt.

Data Analysis and Result Discussion

Demographic Analysis

Table 1: Respondents' Demographic Characteristics

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	68	58.12
	Female	49	41.88
Age	Below 25 years	12	10.26
	25–34 years	39	33.33
	35–44 years	41	35.04
	45 years & above	25	21.37
Marital Status	Single	44	37.61
	Married	63	53.85
	Others	10	8.54
Educational Qualification	SSCE	21	17.95
	ND/NCE	34	29.06
	HND/BSc	47	40.17
	Postgraduate	15	12.82
Position in Business	Owner	71	60.68
	Manager	30	25.64

Years of Business Experience	Supervisor	16	13.68
	Below 5 years	29	24.79
	5–10 years	46	39.32
	Above 10 years	42	35.89
Business Size (Employees)	1–5	48	41.03
	6–10	39	33.33
	Above 10	30	25.64
Business Ownership Type	Sole Proprietorship	69	58.97
	Partnership	31	26.50
	Limited Company	17	14.53

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 1 shows that 68 respondents (58.12%) were male, while 49 (41.88%) were female. Respondents aged 35–44 years accounted for the highest frequency with 41 (35.04%), followed by those aged 25–34 years with 39 (33.33%). Married respondents dominated the study with 63 (53.85%), while singles were 44 (37.61%). In terms of education, 47 respondents (40.17%) possessed HND/BSc qualifications, indicating a relatively educated workforce. Business owners constituted 71 respondents (60.68%), while managers accounted for 30 (25.64%). Respondents with 5–10 years of experience were the majority at 46 (39.32%). Small-sized bakeries employing 1–5 workers formed 48 respondents (41.03%), and sole proprietorships were predominant with 69 respondents (58.97%).

Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between green business models and the creativity of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria? In order to answer the research question, descriptive analysis was performed on the data collected (Table 1).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Green Business Models and Creativity

Item Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD
Green practices encourage new product ideas	32 (27.35)	48 (41.03)	14 (11.97)	13 (11.11)	10 (8.55)
Eco-friendly processes improve creative baking methods	29 (24.79)	52 (44.44)	15 (12.82)	11 (9.40)	8 (6.84)
Waste reduction inspires innovative solutions	35 (29.91)	46 (39.32)	16 (13.68)	12 (10.26)	6 (5.13)
Green models enhance creative problem-solving	31 (26.50)	49 (41.88)	18 (15.38)	10 (8.55)	7 (5.98)

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 2 indicates that respondents largely agreed that green business models enhance creativity in bakery businesses. For item one, 48 respondents (41.03%) agreed, and 32 (27.35%) strongly agreed that green practices encourage new product ideas. Similarly, 52 respondents (44.44%) agreed that eco-friendly processes improve creative baking methods, while 29 (24.79%) strongly agreed. On waste reduction inspiring innovation, 46 respondents (39.32%) agreed, and 35 (29.91%) strongly agreed. Furthermore, 49 respondents (41.88%) agreed that green business models enhance creative problem-solving, with 31 (26.50%) strongly agreeing. Undecided and disagreement responses across all items remained relatively low, indicating limited uncertainty or opposition.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between green business models and the risk-taking of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria? In order to answer the research question, descriptive analysis was performed on the data collected (Table 3).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on Green Business Models and Risk-Taking

Item Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD
Green practices encourage taking business risks	30 (25.64)	51 (43.59)	16 (13.68)	11 (9.40)	9 (7.69)
Investing in eco-friendly tools involves calculated risk	28 (23.93)	54 (46.15)	14 (11.97)	12 (10.26)	7 (5.98)
Green innovation motivates risk-based decisions	33 (28.21)	47 (40.17)	18 (15.38)	11 (9.40)	6 (5.13)
Environmental initiatives increase willingness to experiment	29 (24.79)	50 (42.74)	17 (14.53)	13 (11.11)	8 (6.84)

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 3 reveals that most respondents perceived a positive relationship between green business models and risk-taking among bakery businesses. For item one, 51 respondents (43.59%) agreed, and 30 (25.64%) strongly agreed that green practices encourage business risk-taking. Similarly, 54 respondents (46.15%) agreed that investing in eco-friendly tools involves calculated risk, while 28 (23.93%) strongly agreed. On green innovation motivating risk-based decisions, 47 respondents (40.17%) agreed, and 33 (28.21%) strongly agreed. Furthermore, 50 respondents (42.74%) agreed that environmental initiatives increase willingness to experiment, with 29 (24.79%) strongly agreeing. Undecided and disagreement responses were comparatively low across all items.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between green business models and research and development of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria? In order to answer the research question, descriptive analysis was performed on the data collected (Table 4).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on Green Business Models and Research & Development

Item Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD
Green practices support continuous product research	31 (26.50)	50 (42.74)	17 (14.53)	11 (9.40)	8 (6.84)
Eco-friendly ideas encourage process development	28 (23.93)	53 (45.30)	15 (12.82)	13 (11.11)	8 (6.84)
Green models increase investment in new baking methods	34 (29.06)	48 (41.03)	16 (13.68)	12 (10.26)	7 (5.98)
Environmental focus improves research planning	30 (25.64)	51 (43.59)	18 (15.38)	10 (8.55)	8 (6.84)

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Table 4 shows that respondents largely agreed that green business models positively influence research and development activities in bakery businesses. For item one, 50 respondents (42.74%) agreed, and 31 (26.50%) strongly agreed that green practices support continuous product research. Similarly, 53 respondents (45.30%) agreed that eco-friendly ideas encourage process development, while 28 (23.93%) strongly agreed. On investment in new baking methods, 48 respondents (41.03%) agreed, and 34 (29.06%) strongly agreed. Furthermore, 51 respondents (43.59%) agreed that environmental focus improves research planning, with 30 (25.64%) strongly agreeing. Undecided and disagreement responses across the items were relatively minimal.

Testing of Hypotheses

H₀₁: The null hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between green business models and the creativity of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. In order to test the hypothesis, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis was performed on the data (Table 5).

Table 5: Pearson Correlation between Green Business Models and Creativity

Variables		Green Business Models	Creativity
Market Development Strategies	Pearson Correlation	1	.68**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	—	0.000
	N	117	117
Revenue Growth	Pearson Correlation	.68**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	—
	N	117	117

**** Significant at 0.05 level; df = 115; N = 117; Critical r-value = 0.182**

a. Dependent Variable: Creativity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Green Business Models

Table 5 shows a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.68, indicating a strong positive relationship between green business models and creativity of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The calculated r-value (0.68) is greater than the critical r-value (0.182) at the 0.05 level of significance with 115 degrees of freedom. In addition, the significance value (p = 0.000) is less than 0.05. Based on these results, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that green business models significantly enhance creativity among bakery businesses, suggesting that environmentally friendly practices stimulate innovative ideas, creative processes, and problem-solving within the sector.

H₀₂: The null hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between green business models and the risk-taking of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. In order to test the hypothesis, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis was performed on the data (Table 6).

Table 6: Pearson Correlation between Green Business Models and Risk-Taking

Variables		Green Business Models	Creativity
Market Development Strategies	Pearson Correlation	1	.62**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	—	0.000
	N	117	117
Revenue Growth	Pearson Correlation	.62**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	—
	N	117	117

**** Significant at 0.05 level; df = 115; N = 117; Critical r-value = 0.182**

a. Dependent Variable: Risk-Taking

b. Predictors: (Constant), Green Business Models

Table 6 reveals a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.62, indicating a strong positive relationship between green business models and risk-taking among bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The calculated r -value (0.62) is greater than the critical r -value (0.182) at the 0.05 level of significance with 115 degrees of freedom. Additionally, the probability value ($p = 0.000$) is less than 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected. This result implies that the adoption of green business models significantly influences risk-taking behavior, encouraging bakery businesses to engage in calculated risks such as investing in eco-friendly technologies and experimenting with innovative production methods.

H₀₃: The null hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between green business models and the research and development activities of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. In order to test the hypothesis, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis was performed on the data (Table 7).

Table 7: Pearson Correlation between Green Business Models and Research & Development

Variables		Green Business Models	Creativity
Market Development Strategies	Pearson Correlation	1	.71**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	—	0.000
	N	117	117
Revenue Growth	Pearson Correlation	.71**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	—
	N	117	117

** Significant at 0.05 level; $df = 115$; $N = 117$; Critical r -value = 0.182

a. Dependent Variable: Research & Development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Green Business Models

Table 7 indicates a strong positive relationship between green business models and research and development activities of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, with a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.71. The calculated r -value (0.71) exceeds the critical r -value (0.182) at the 0.05 level of significance with 115 degrees of freedom. Furthermore, the significance value ($p = 0.000$) is less than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This finding suggests that the adoption of green business models significantly enhances research and development efforts, encouraging continuous product improvement, innovative baking methods, and environmentally focused process development among bakery businesses.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed a significant positive relationship between green business models and the creativity of bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. This result aligns with the theoretical expectation of Schumpeter's Innovation Theory, which posits that innovation and creativity are driven by new combinations of resources and processes. The adoption of green practices compels firms to rethink production methods, waste management, and product design, thereby stimulating creative outcomes. Empirically, this finding is consistent with the studies of Adeleke and Aminu (2021) and Eneh (2019), who found that environmentally sustainable practices enhance creativity and innovation among small and medium enterprises. Similarly, Chen, Chang, and Lin (2014) reported that green innovation significantly improves firms' creative capabilities, suggesting that environmental responsibility serves as a catalyst for innovative thinking.

The second finding demonstrated a significant relationship between green business models and risk-taking behavior among bakery businesses. This outcome supports Entrepreneurial Orientation Theory, which identifies risk-taking as a key dimension of entrepreneurial behavior. Engaging in green initiatives often requires investment in new technologies and processes, which inherently involves calculated risks. The result corroborates empirical evidence from Lumpkin and Dess (1996) and Kraus et al. (2012), who reported that sustainability-oriented entrepreneurship increases firms' willingness to take strategic risks. Furthermore, Eshima and Anderson (2017) observed that environmentally driven firms are more inclined to experiment with new business models, reinforcing the notion that green practices encourage proactive and risk-oriented decision-making.

The third finding indicated a strong positive relationship between green business models and research and development (R&D) activities. This finding is consistent with the Resource-Based View (RBV), which suggests that investment in unique and valuable resources, such as green knowledge and eco-innovation capabilities, enhances organizational competitiveness. The result supports prior empirical studies by Horbach, Rammer, and Rennings (2012) and OECD (2018), which established that environmental sustainability initiatives stimulate R&D investments and technological advancement. Similarly, Dangelico and Pujari (2010) found that green product development encourages continuous research and process improvement. Thus, the study confirms that green business models serve as a strategic driver of sustained research and development efforts in bakery businesses.

Conclusion

This study examined how entrepreneurial initiatives foster green business models among bakery businesses in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, focusing on creativity, risk-taking, and research and development (R&D) activities. The findings revealed that green business models significantly enhance creativity, encouraging bakery owners and employees to develop innovative products, improve baking processes, and adopt environmentally friendly solutions. Similarly, the study established a positive relationship between green business models and risk-taking behavior, indicating that environmentally conscious practices motivate bakery businesses to undertake calculated risks, invest in new technologies, and explore novel operational methods. Furthermore, the study demonstrated that green business models positively influence research and development, prompting continuous investment in product improvement, sustainable processes, and eco-innovation initiatives. These findings corroborate theoretical expectations, such as Schumpeter's Innovation Theory, Entrepreneurial Orientation Theory, and the Resource-Based View, and align with prior empirical studies that highlight the role of sustainability in driving creativity, innovation, and strategic risk-taking among enterprises. Overall, the study confirms that green business models are not only environmentally beneficial but also serve as strategic tools for enhancing entrepreneurial performance and competitiveness in the bakery sector. This underscores the importance of integrating sustainability with entrepreneurial initiatives to ensure long-term growth and environmental responsibility.

Recommendations

1. Bakery Business Owners and Managers should prioritize the adoption of green business models by implementing eco-friendly processes, waste reduction strategies, and innovative product development to enhance creativity, risk-taking, and R&D activities.

2. Entrepreneurial and Small Business Support Agencies should provide training, advisory services, and funding for bakeries to implement sustainable practices, encouraging innovation and calculated risk-taking.
3. Policy Makers and Regulatory Bodies should create incentives such as tax relief, grants, or recognition programs for bakery businesses that adopt environmentally sustainable models to promote green entrepreneurship.
4. Academic and Research Institutions should support empirical research on green innovation in small and medium enterprises to generate insights for improving business sustainability and competitiveness.

Limitations, Validity, and Credibility

The study was limited to bakery businesses within Port Harcourt, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other regions or sectors. Validity was ensured through face and content validation of the questionnaire by experts in entrepreneurship and environmental management, guaranteeing that items accurately measured creativity, risk-taking, and R&D in relation to green business models. Credibility was established by using a reliable instrument (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.82) and ensuring a high response rate (95.1%), enhancing the accuracy and trustworthiness of the data collected.

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